

REARING AND FEEDING LOCAL TURKEYS IN UZBEKISTAN

To'remuratov Dauletiyar

Master student of the Karakalpak Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7445179>

Abstract. This article reveals the local turkeys living in Uzbekistan, about dry feeding of heavy weight turkeys and bronze turkeys, changing their temperature according to their age and number of practical works that have been researched.

Key words: breeding, temperature, growth, air, bronze turkey, white turkey, chick turkey.

Turkeys are birds which gives meat. There different types of meat production turkeys; they are heavy, medium and light types. Heavy-type turkeys product a lot of meat which are used in a variety of dishes. Turkeys of medium type are used in farms. In 1871 wild American turkeys were crossed with English turkeys. The record weight was 85.7 kg. The reason this breed was not widely distributed, it was black in color and black spots on the body after slaughtering reduced the quality of meat white with a wide breast. The turkey breed is widespread in Uzbekistan and foreign countries and it is possible to obtain hybrids of light, medium and heavy weight turkeys. The creation of crosses and breeds is widely used. The turkey is an important in the agricultural sphere that is largely used as a meat type bird as egg production. Turkey is the second largest contributor to the world's poultry meat production after chicken.

Uzbek local turkeys: bronze and white turkeys are the most distributed types of these species in Uzbekistan. Bronze turkey by type and weight is similar with North Caucasian bronze one. Weight of one-year-old turkeycocks is 10-12 kg, female ones up to 6-8 kg; egg productivity varies from 50 to 100 eggs. Fecundation ability and survival rate are high. Plumage on neck and the top part of breast of males is dark brown with red-black hue. Feathers on back are black with wide brilliant stripe of bronze shade. Visible steering feathers are black with narrow cross brown strips. The ends of feathers are white. Wing-feathers are black with white strips. At optimum feeding young turkey reaches to its commodity weight after 6 month-age. The body weight of males makes 6-6.5 kg, and for females 4-5 kg. White turkey: breeding of white coloured turkey began after delivery to Uzbekistan of North Caucasian white turkey, selecting the bestones on their acclimatization also crossing North Caucasian white females with bronze males. Body weight of adult turkey cocks is 14-16 kg, females 7-9 kg. They have compact, lengthened trunk, deep breast and pure white plumage. Uzbek white female turkeys have high egg productivity is 60 -120 eggs per a year, satisfactory reproductive qualities, rather good meat precocity and good commodity conditions of body atearly age with a white skin. The body weight of 6 month turkey reaches for males' 7-7.5 kg and for females 5-5.5 kg.

Feed rate for 1 chicken in 1 day in dry feeding of heavy weight turkeys.

Turkey age (week)	Feed rate (g)	Turkey age (week)	Feed rate (g)
1	10	13	265

2	25	14	280
3	40	15	290
4	60	16	310
5	90	17	325
6	120	18	220
7	150	19	240
8	165	20	260
9	195	21	280
10	220	22	285
11	250	23-24	290
12	260	25-30	280

Bronze breed and live weight of turkey

Nº	Name	age (day)	live weight
1	Turkey chick	1	50-52
2	Turkey chick	20	125
	Turkey chick	30	400
4	Turkey chick	50	850
5	Turkey chick	70	1500
6	Turkey chick	90	2500
7	A young male turkey	110	3900
8	A young female turkey	110	3000
9	A young male turkey	130	4800
10	A young female turkey	130	3500
11	A young male turkey	150	5800
12	A young female turkey	150	3800

Approximate room temperature for keeping turkey chicks.

Nº	Turkeys age (day)	Room temperature (t°c)
1	1-6	33-34
2	8-10	30-31
3	12-20	27-29
4	22-30	23-25
5	32-40	21-22

Chalk, nutritious lime (limestone) shell and small stone.

It is very useful to feed young turkeys from the age of 1.5-2 months with grown grain rich in vitamin B. Chalk, shell and small stones should always be in the feed.

Nº	Turkeys age (week)	Stone size
1	1-2	2-3
2	3-7	4-5
3	8-12	5-7

4	12-13 and above	10 hashes
---	-----------------	-----------

When feeding turkey chicks with dry food, starting from 5 days old, it is necessary to pay attention to adding small stones to the feed twice a week, in the amount of 1-3 percent of the total diet. The addition of small stones to the diet prevents young turkeys from scratching each other's feathers and eating bedding and prevents the formation of blockages in the gastrointestinal tract.

References:

1. S.Islomxodjayev, K.Boboyev, K.G'ulomov «Parrandachilikda amaliy mashg'ulotlar» T.«Uzbekistan »1996 y.
2. A.X.Xolmatov, M.Uroqov "Agrobank" ATB 100 kitob to'plami. Kurkachilik 83-kitob Toshkent-2021.
3. Bogolyubskiy S.I. «Selekciya selskoxozyavstvennoy ptici» M. «Agropromizdat»1991 y.
4. Fisinin G.A, Tardatyan M. «Promishlennoe pticevodstvo» M. Kolos 1990.

